

Legislative Position On The Principle Of Free Public Utility Services

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Public Utility, Free Services, Constitutional Texts, Draw, Tariffs, Administrative Facilities, Allowances</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5805292</p>	<p><i>As a result of the developments that have occurred in society, the needs of individuals have increased in basic essential services that they are not able to provide alone, prompting the state to transform from a guardian state that performs the function of security and defense to a state interfering in economic and social life. It is responsible for providing the basic needs of the public of citizens, but that facility differs in terms of types and nature, in terms of type it is administrative service facilities, economic facilities (commercial and industrial), and professional facilities, and in terms of nature they are facilities that provide their services to the public in return for a price, which is What is represented by economic facilities, as for professional facilities, they are the ones that organize the work of one of the professions, and finally the service administrative facilities are those that provide their services to the public free of charge. However, in special cases, the state goes to provide its services in those facilities in exchange for a price that the beneficiaries obtain from it with a blind eye to what is stated in the constitution of texts that prove free of charge Ha, which prompted us to weigh these acts in the installments of the law to show the extent of their legitimacy. These actions are inconsistent with the provisions of the constitution, and also go to the inequality between individuals in receiving services from those facilities.</i></p>

Introduction

The developments that have occurred in the lives of individuals in society have prompted the development of the state's function and the increase in the burdens placed upon it. As a result of the multiplicity and different needs of individuals in terms of the environment and the conditions in which they live, it needs the state's contribution with all its institutions to provide these needs, especially the necessary ones, as it is unable to meet those needs. The requirements and needs himself, and the higher the standard of living of individuals, the greater their requirements for public services. Which led to the expansion of the scope of the state, the development of its function, and the increase in the burdens placed on it. This is through the emergence of public utilities through which the state assumes the new role until it has become called the state of public utilities. There are many types of public utilities, including administrative public utilities, and commercial public utilities and industrial (economic), and professional public utilities. The nature of the services provided by those facilities also varied. If the constitution stipulates that the services provided by some facilities are free of charge, on the other hand, we see public facilities that provide their services for a price. As a result of economic conditions that may occur in a country, it becomes difficult to provide free services to the fullest, and according to what is stated in the constitution, the administration, as a result, goes to address the existing situation in other ways that seek to obtain financial resources to maintain and continue the functioning of the public facility, such as collecting the public price. In return for the entire service, meaning that the state does not deduct any amount from its budget, but rather it falls on the shoulders of the beneficiary, and sometimes the amounts paid exceed the expenses of the services provided. However, what the administration of the public utility does in this way may contradict what is stated in the constitution, since the public utilities' finances receive From the state budget law and from the fees imposed on the beneficiaries of its services.

2- The importance of research:

The importance of research in the field of public utility services lies in the great role that these facilities play in providing basic services to the public of citizens, which are the backbone in the stability of public life, which the public administration is responsible for establishing, organizing and supervising, as well as the desire to highlight the extent of interest that the legislation attaches to some Countries in the field of clarifying the nature of the beneficiaries receiving public utility services, since there are public utilities that provide their services for free, and there are those who are satisfied with fees, and others are based on the payment of the price of services.

3 - The problem of research:

In light of the affirmation of the Constitution of the Republic of Iraq for the year 2005 on reforming the Iraqi economy according to modern foundations, and in order to ensure the full investment of its resources while

encouraging the private sector, we note the absence of an integrated legislative vision in the development of public utility management while taking advantage of indirect methods in management, as well as the inadequacy of legislation. The current issue of setting legal rules that keep pace with recent developments that tend to limit the application of the principle of free public utility services, and its reflection on the functioning of services provided to individuals.

4- Research Methodology:

In this research, we will rely on the analytical method of legal texts and the opinions of jurists, and we will follow the comparative method with France and Egypt, due to the rich experience that those countries, especially France, have at the legislative level and judicial rulings. Therefore, we intended to include in our research a comparative study with France, Egypt and Iraq, despite the difficulty we faced in the search due to the scarcity of sources that dealt with the subject of free services in public utilities.

5- Research plan:

We will divide our research into two sections, in the first of which we will discuss the principle of free public utilities and the legislative position for them in two demands. Public utilities in a first requirement. We will single out the second requirement to indicate the competent authority to determine the value of the allowance. Let's end our research with a conclusion in which we show the most important results we have reached. At the same time, we will present the necessary recommendations for that.

The first topic: the principle of free public utility services and the constitutional basis of it.

There are many types of public utilities, including administrative public utilities, commercial and industrial (economic) public utilities, and professional public utilities. The nature of the services provided by those facilities also varied. If the constitution stipulates that the services provided by some facilities are free of charge, on the other hand, we see public facilities that provide their services for a price. As a result of economic conditions that may occur in a country, it becomes difficult to provide free services to the fullest extent, according to what is stated in the constitution. Therefore, we divided our study into two demands, in the first of which we deal with the principle of free public utility services, and we allocated the second requirement to clarify the constitutional and legal basis for the principle of free.

The first requirement: the principle of free public utility services.

Section one: the concept of free public utility services.

If we look at the public utility through the lens of the economic concept, we certainly find that the free nature is strange and far from it. If there is no (price) for some facilities, then all of them certainly have a (cost). In all cases, the question remains about knowing who should bear the amount of this cost. Here, we have two main possibilities:

A -As for it being borne by the total of the taxpayers represented by the state treasury, then the public utility performs its services free of charge, and it is said that it is free of charge.

B -As for it to be borne by the beneficiaries or beneficiaries of the services, then it is said about the public facility that it is not free.

But this distinction remains in fact an approximation is not fixed, considering that the two possibilities together are not fixed and they are subject to adaptation and change.

If the public utility is free, then its cost is paid, as we said, from the treasury funds by opening allocations for this purpose in the general budget. Which is what we meant by saying that the total of the taxpayers secure coverage of the expenses incurred as a result of performing services because they are the ones who feed the treasury and secure resources in the general budget (KhourySaad Allah, 1999, p. 244).

If this facility is not free, here it is necessary to know who bears the expenses:

A -Either it is borne by all consumers and users equally or unevenly.

B -Or it is borne only by some of those without the others.

In all cases, a distinction must be made between the free public utility itself and the free services it provides. The public utility may not be free, but its services are free for some of those concerned with it. Where, in the end, it is paid for, either by the guarantee fund, or by the state or people of public law through the social

assistance it grants to its employees and workers. The choice between these possibilities is subject to many justifications, but they are divided between two major categories of elements and reasons: the category of technical elements and the category of political reasons.

First: the technical elements: these elements are related to the nature of the service performed by the facility, which is unable to pay or pay its cost unless it is linked to a personal or individual nature. However, the technical nature of choosing between a free public facility and another that is not free, is not subject to a fixed standard, but is relative, and varies between This or that type of service to be provided and the interests to be protected, so this character did not meet the need, it must be supplemented with political reasons that may be important to the subject.

Second: Political reasons: This stems from the concept of social solidarity, which is the basis for the existence of the modern state of law, which bears the responsibility of providing everything that the citizen cannot provide for himself. dignity, as well as protecting the rights of citizens and warding off dangers from them. These matters are among the tasks of the state, and therefore it alone bears the expenses incurred as a result of them (Al-Tamawi Suleiman, 1979, p. 313). But on the other hand, there are some public utilities that provide a certain type of services and are in essence of a general nature. However, in the end they benefit only the people who benefit from them. As a result of developments in the field of life and social matters, we see that there are free public utilities, but they constitute a minority if they are Compare it to non-free public utilities, which are constantly increasing.

The second subsection: the decline of the free nature of public utilities.

The texts of some international declarations dealt with the public facility with some ambiguity that makes it oscillate between free and non-free, i.e. permitting both cases, and among those texts what was stated in Article 13 of the Declaration on the Rights of Man and the French Citizen (in order to secure the expenditures of public power, and those related to administration, a contribution must be made general in it). It is inferred from that text that he preferred the free without ruling out the opposite.

The gold of jurisprudence (Al-KhourySaad Allah, 1999, p. 48).To consider the rule of free jurisprudence adhered to by the great men of jurisprudence, but quickly retracted strongly in the face of the reality of the situation. The jurist Horio considered that the salient feature of public utilities is their non-free nature of their association with the state as a public authority and not an ordinary personand he held that the state as a public authority is not (an association that produces profit and wealth) and it is not permissible for it to sells its production, but as a result, he found himself forced to admit that there are public utilities that have a commercial activity, and that those facilities charge fees or allowances for their services, but this does not negate the principle of freebies, given that these facilities do not make profits, so the financing through the imposition of taxes And its fulfillment alone is enough to achieve the principle of equality before public utilities (Hauriou, 1900, p. 47).

The jurist Horio also argued that although there are public utilities that make profits in exchange for providing their services to the public, these utilities are not free and few to the extent that the prevailing belief was that they are on the way to extinction (see law, 17 mar, 1827). Especially after the issuance of the 1881 law that imposed free education and abolished the traffic fee, so the allowances paid for services were considered as a fee recorded in the imports of the state treasury (Hauriou; S.1900-11-146.).

As for the jurist Deji, he implicitly assumed that public utilities would not be free when he launched the idea of decentralization regarding them, assuming that this decentralization is based on the possession of real estate and funds that are managed and invested by his employees in return for their participation in the profits as a reward for them for good management and investment (Duguit, 1932). , p.83). From here, the theory of freebies was the most preponderant, because in all cases it was consistent and consistent at that time with the concept of a liberal state whose economic activity was limited to non-commercial sectors that do not sell their production and, therefore, do not receive the price of their goods and services directly (Beaulieu, 1905, P. 4).

All of this was behind the conviction of the French jurisprudence in the theory of freebies, but it soon retreated in front of the increase in non-free public utilities due to the development of the concept of the modern state, which emerged in different ways, for example:

1 - The proliferation of public utilities of an industrial and commercial nature, which are very similar to private commercial and industrial activities, and charge a price for providing their services, which would make a profit.

2 - The state's transformation from a guard to an interventionist led to an increase in the number of public utilities, which in turn caused financial pressure and then the need to cover those exorbitant expenses, which became the state's duty to bear to meet the needs of society and achieve the public interest, and at the same time it required the creation of new facilities. This prompted the state to collect fees and impose fees and tariffs on beneficiaries and consumers (Prelot, 1951, p159)).

3 - Some jurisprudence went to consider freeness as a doctrine for achieving absolute equality that does not distinguish between rich and poor. However, the reality of the situation shows otherwise, for example that what

was reported about free higher education in France, but it seems far from reality because the beneficiaries of that The facility is only the rich and middle class and the poor are deprived of that, and this is what prompted jurisprudence to say that it is necessary to impose allowances and tariffs on the services of the university facility so that it can organize itself in this field and lay practical foundations that enable it to resort to taking into account the material situation of each of the three groups in society, the affluent, the middle class and the poor, so the latter is completely exempted or pays what is Only symbolic, while the other two categories are charged with fees ranging from an upper and lower bound according to the social and financial status of each of them (A.Mine, 1987, p, 204)).

4- Imposing a price or allowances for utilities services, for the purpose of enhancing the financial balance of the facility between its revenues and expenditures, to achieve financial and administrative independence, and to work on creating other public utilities to increase the chances of achieving the public benefit (G.Ardant, 1953, p.39)).

All this prompted the saying that giving up free public utilities is better than their existence, and this cannot be considered as having a negative impact on the principle of equality, but rather it can be included in the category of the modern state as an important element of the neutral state, which is what prompts the legislator in some countries today. To adopt the free nature of the utilities services and impose a corresponding financial allowance according to the degree of their importance. If jurisprudence demands the necessity of abandoning the principle of freeness, we must show the comprehensiveness of the free nature of public utilities and the limited exceptions that may occur to it in the light of both constitutional and legislative texts.

From the above, it can be said that the free nature is not one of the general principles that govern the functioning and activity of the public utility, which is evident in the economic public utilities (industrial and commercial) that perform their services in return for fees and tariffs imposed by laws and regulations for their continuity and sustainability. This means that administrative facilities are excluded from the principle of free of charge, which provide their services for free, for free here is not a principle that is only relatively applicable in some administrative public facilities, specifically whose benefits and services are imposed on them towards their beneficiaries, because these benefits and services are obligatory on the management of these facilities and bear the burdens. The principle of freebies here is generally applied in the case where the beneficiaries of the public utility have received the services entrusted to it in the light of the requirements of the public interest, and here the work of the administration is not considered legitimate if it received allowances or fees from the beneficiaries of those facilities (Al-Khoury, 1988, p. 255).

The second requirement: the constitutional and legal basis for the principle of free public utility.

It is clear from the entirety of what the jurisprudence said and reached and settled upon by diligence on the subject, that there are absolutely no general rules that take into account the reward of public utilities, i.e. payment of a fee or a tariff for its services. year to year, according to the quality and importance of the services it provides. On the contrary, we see that there are some texts that impose free, but they are few and rare.

Section one: the constitutional basis.

The introduction to the French Constitution of 1958 stated that the public education facility should be free when it stated that “the organization of free and secular teaching in the public sector and at all levels is a duty and imposed on the state.” In response to this, the free higher education in France is based on a constitutional basis in most French universities. However, this rule did not take education for free in general, but rather In return, the administration collected university fees, which was the practice of the French Constitutional Council, which is the body that monitors the constitutionality of laws. (C.E.dec 1984, p.399).

This means that the existence of the free base does not mean dispensing with the imposition of any fee or the necessity of not rejecting it. There may remain, and in light of its existence, some minor fees that must be charged to students, and that what the student pays in this regard remains below the real level of cost or what the administration bears. Undergraduate burdens. In any case, the free nature of higher education is usually limited to certificates granted by national universities only, excluding those obtained by the student from abroad. And the free base, which is one of the most important characteristics of this facility, remains semi-isolated and mostly not generalized. The jurisprudence is almost unanimously agreed that the constitution’s inclusion of texts that impose free access to some rights and services does not necessarily and necessarily mean that the public utilities entrusted with achieving these services should be free (Houriou, 1900, p.47).

This is because there are other means capable of securing what is required, even indirectly, such as aid and financial contributions granted by the state, for example, to beneficiaries and consumers. In addition, the French Constitutional Council recognizes the constitutionality of the allowances paid by individuals for their access to

services, considering that the latter is considered the pillar or bond. legal justification for the imposition of the payment of these allowances.

In Egypt, it is known that one of the principles that govern public utilities is the principle of equality of citizens to benefit from their services. It was mentioned in the preamble to the Egyptian Constitution of 2014, which is in force, to achieve equality between individuals in rights and duties without any discrimination. Article (4) of the Constitution stipulates (...its national unity, which is based on the principles of equality, justice and equal opportunities for all citizens, in the manner set forth in the Constitution. And based on the provisions of the constitution, Egypt has also guaranteed free health services to all citizens, which are provided by public health facilities, which are semi-administrative public facilities. The state guarantees the maintenance of public health services facilities that provide their services to the people, supporting them and working to raise their efficiency and equitable geographical spread). Here, the text shows the implicit recognition of free health services for citizens and ensuring the provision of funds necessary to maintain health facilities in order to raise their efficiency and the quality of their services, considering the state From those charged with this, excluding the beneficiaries, who represent the class of the people, and in the field of educational facilities, the Constitution affirmed that education is free and compulsory. It is compulsory until the end of the secondary stage or its equivalent, and the state guarantees that it is free of charge in its various stages in the state's educational institutions, in accordance with the law. The state is obligated to allocate a percentage of government spending for education that is not less than 4% of the gross national product) As for Article (21) it stipulates (. the state guarantees the provision of university education in accordance with international quality standards, and works on

Developing university education, and guaranteeing it is free in state universities and institutes, in accordance with the law. By examining the texts of the constitution, we see that the state provides semi-administrative public utility services, including health, education and higher education, free of charge to the public, and guarantees the provision of funds necessary for the continuation of these services. It is recognized that the facility is a public facility, and it is not required that the services it provides be free for all. Rather, it may impose a fee to be paid by each beneficiary without losing its administrative capacity and turning it into an economic facility, but in all cases the fee should not be excessive, so that the facility comes out of its generality and the purpose for which it was created, which is the public interest. The payment of fees is in exchange for using the services of these facilities, so these fees are not considered an end in themselves, but rather to regulate the use of the services of individuals from the facility on the one hand, and to relieve some of the burdens on the state's general budget on the other hand, and this did not raise any problem or legal difficulty in the past. The traditional public utilities were purely administrative public utilities (BoujamaaRadwan, 2000, p. 57). It is generally noted that the legislator sought to expand the scope of free public utilities (Abdul Basset, 1989, p. 112).

In Iraq, the effective constitution of 2005 contained explicit and implicit texts showing the provision of free services to semi-administrative public utilities. It came in Article (31) first: (Every Iraqi has the right to health care, and the state is concerned with public health. Means of prevention and treatment are guaranteed by the establishment of various hospitals and health institutions) . Although there is no explicit provision for free health services, it is understood from the text of the article that state guarantees for means of prevention and treatment is an implicit provision for providing services for free. It shall also, in accordance with this text, establish health institutions that undertake the provision of health services. Article 34 states first: "Education is a basic factor for the progress of society and a right guaranteed by the state, and it is mandatory in the primary stage." As for the second paragraph of this article, it states: "Free education is a right for all Iraqis in its various stages." We conclude from this that the public health, educational, and higher education facilities are free of charge, and they are semi-administrative service public facilities that provide their services free of charge according to the text of the constitution. It should be mentioned here that the services of a public health facility are in return for fees collected by the beneficiaries of the services so that the facility can organize itself and provide the best services, especially that the deterioration of the economic conditions of the country affects the material income of the individual as well as the failure to provide services in terms that the administrative public facilities It depends on the budget assigned to it in accordance with the state's general budget law. If the constitution is the supreme law in any country and the constitutional base is at the top of the legal organization hierarchy, then the laws are legislated in implementation of the provisions of the constitution, except that there are legislative texts that have been enacted to regulate the work of public utilities that contradict the provisions of the constitution.

Section Two: The Legislative Basis

There are some legislations that oblige the administration not to free its facilities, at least implicitly, and sometimes explicitly.

In France, some laws imposed a financial balance in the budget of public utilities, including the municipal utility, and thus the balance of local public utilities of an economic nature, and this means that the beneficiary of public utility services must pay a certain allowance as a price for the utility service rendered to them, which is what came in Law 5 January 1988, which deliberately mitigated the severity of this rule without disrupting it or touching its essence. And if this equilibrium rule is not often applied, this does not preclude continuing to loan tariffs or allowances on utility services.

As well as what was stated in the law of health slaughterhouses No. 8 of July of 1965, which states that the services provided by public health slaughterhouses are not free but rather paid (J. Carles et J. Dupuis, 1989, p56).

In Iraq, the laws of some institutions of the Ministry of Interior, which is a purely administrative facility, indicated that fees are charged for services provided to individuals. The General Traffic Directorate, in its Law No. 8 of 2019, went to collect fees for the services it provides. Article 18 / first indicated that the fees stipulated for them in this law. Article 43 of the same law also clarifies the mechanism for dividing the amounts of fees collected from citizens between each of the state treasury and a department employed to develop traffic and secure its requirements. And another section of the Directorate of Roads and Bridges from in order to perpetuation.

It also dealt with the General Passport Law No. 32 of 2015 in its article 8, provided that the Directorate collects a fee when issuing the passport.

for the Public Municipalities Facility, it issued a special law for collecting fees called the Public Municipal Revenue Law on November 22, 2016. It stipulated in Article 8/First that the competent authorities are the ones who decide what wages must be collected in exchange for the services provided by the municipality.

The Electricity Utility Law No. 53 of 2017 also addressed in Article 2 that the service provided to the beneficiaries is in return for a certain fee.

After all, it is clear that there is solidarity between the administration and the individuals in the permanence of the work of the public utilities and the continuity of their work, as it was clear from the third and fourth items of the same article that the state has directed, in its management of this facility, to the participation of the private sector, whether national or foreign, by investing in the field of production and distribution. This is for the sake of the continuity of that facility and the permanence of its regular and steady progress due to the importance it carries in the lives of individuals.

From all this it is clear that public utilities, of whatever type, administratively or economically, do not provide their services for free without imposing some tariffs on the provision of those services, in order to maintain these public utilities and prevent failure to perform their services. It is also clear that the administration has tended in some The situation has led to the involvement of the private sector in the work of these facilities, and this means that these facilities have burdened the state treasury, which prompted it to move in this direction.

The second topic: the authority competent to impose and determine allowances.

First requirement: the authority competent to impose allowances and their types.

In this requirement, we will address the statement of the authority concerned with imposing allowances for the services provided by public utilities, and we will discuss in the second section an indication of the types of allowances and the distinction between them.

Section one: The authority competent to impose allowances.

It is clear from the foregoing that it is up to the legislation to impose the free nature of the public utility, and it can also cancel it if it exists.

In principle, it is up to the legislation alone to impose a tax, fee, or tariff on any service or benefit provided by a public utility.

In France, the pronouncement of Article 34 of the French Constitution states that it is not permissible to impose a tax and determine its amount and methods of collecting it except by law, and therefore in this case a law must be issued based on the above article in which it determines the fees and tariffs imposed on beneficiaries of public utility services. This means that the constitutional legislator leaves According to Article 34, financial legislation or laws may determine the state's resources and burdens in accordance with the specific conditions established

by law. Therefore, in France, the Legislative Decree (No. 2-59) issued on January 2, 1959, which is the basic law relating to the rules that must be adhered to by financial laws, in implementation of the text of Article 34 of the Constitution. Where this law stipulated in Article (5) to grant The right to set a tariff or an allowance for services provided by the state through its public utilities, to the procedural authority, that is, by decree instead of the law (G.Conac, p.763).

In Iraq, the pronouncement of Article (28) of the Iraqi constitution in force for the year 2005 states that taxes and fees may not be imposed and cannot be modified, collected or exempted except by law. The law also authorized exempting low-income people from taxes in a way that ensures that the minimum standard of living is not compromised. However, determining the amount of tariffs and allowances such as price, price, tax and others is the responsibility of the administration by issuing executive regulations to facilitate the implementation of laws (Abdul Baset, 1989, p. 45).

In France, Article (21) of the 1958 Constitution of France stipulates that the Prime Minister manages the affairs of the government. He exercises the authority to issue regulations that guarantee the implementation of laws, and he may delegate some of his powers to ministers in this regard.

in Egypt

In Iraq, the Iraqi constitution in force for the year 2005, in its article (80/third), gives the Council of Ministers the authority to issue regulations, instructions and decisions with the aim of implementing laws, and here it can be said that the administration, which determines the allowances, takes into account the material situation of the beneficiaries and the economic situation.

For the country, in the sense that the allowance is commensurate with the importance of the service provision, even if there are allowances taken without there being any service provision, as in the case of tax, and when we say that we see that some public and private utilities, especially administrative ones, have violated the provisions of the constitution and the law when they created channels that we do not find It has a legal adaptation through which services are rendered to the beneficiaries for a price, as in the case of the higher education facility, which is an administrative facility, to create a parallel education channel, for which it charges exorbitant prices that cannot be compared to the services provided by this facility to the beneficiaries. This is a clear violation of Article 34 of the Constitution. Also, the establishment of private wards in hospitals by a public health facility that provides services to beneficiaries in return for prices that may reach a certain extent that private health institutions can meet, which is also a clear violation of Articles 16 and 31 of the Constitution. Therefore, the administration must abide by what the constitution stipulates for it, otherwise many of its actions are illegal.

The second section: Types of allowances.

In light of the foregoing and for further clarification, we must try, even briefly, to analyze the legal concept of tariffs or allowances to be paid in exchange for utility services and what distinguishes them from each other. If the services provided by the state to the public are not always suitable to be a basis for tax, then they are often the basis for other payments made to the beneficiaries in return, and they constitute an important resource for the treasury. There are two types of payments that individuals usually face in this field:

The first type is the cases in which the payment is made by them voluntarily and without coercion, such as paying the price of the commodity, for example.

As for the second type, it is represented in cases in which they have to pay on a specific date under pain of compulsion to do so, and this applies to taxes, fees, and royalties due periodically, i.e. at a specific date.

First: the price (or cost).

The price is an amount that a person pays in return for obtaining a good or service produced by the state's public commercial or industrial enterprises (Ahmed, without a year of publication, pg. 46). The state may depend on securing some services and basic needs in return for a specific price that it determines in advance, to be paid by the beneficiary of the service, just as the buyer pays the price of the commodity to the seller (Younis, 1991, p. 76). It is natural that the sums collected in this way contribute to the financing of public expenditures, similar to taxes, fees and other allowances, but they are distinguished from others in several points, the most important of which are:

1- Prices are paid for materials of an industrial or commercial nature, i.e. for economic facilities, and they are in themselves the purpose of the existence of these facilities (Al-MahjoubRefaat, 1979, p. 480).

2 - The price is paid by the buyer voluntarily and without coercion. The quality of the material offered for sale is sufficient to attract him and urge him to pay, and this means that there is no need for the legislator to intervene in the process of determining the price. Has

It is also determined by a decision issued by the competent administrative authority, and this is what often happens with regard to public economic utilities, without the legislator interfering in that, which facilitates government work with regard to securing monetary financial resources.

However, the distinction between price and other allowances is not always clear and accessible because the legal status of each of these payments is not the same, but there are nevertheless cases in which the criteria for traditional distinction between them are difficult to apply (Khoury Abdullah, 1999, p. 264).

Second: fees and royalties.

The fee means a sum of money that the individual pays to the state or other public bodies forcibly in return for his use of a specific service that it performs for him, which at the same time achieves a private benefit in addition to the public benefit that accrues to society as a result of its performance (Ahmed, without publication year, p. 42). It may happen that the state, in return for the service it performs, requires the payment of a fee or a periodic or seasonal allowance, and they are often confused with price and tax.

As for the royalty, it is a sum of money that the state obtains forcibly from real estate owners who benefited from the value of their real estate as a result of the implementation of a public project (Al-Daqr Rashid, 1962, pg. 49).

It is possible to distinguish between fee, royalty and price. One of the similarities between them is that the fee and royalty are charged like the price or the price in exchange for a special benefit, and the payment is in cash. However, they differ from the price in several respects, the most important of which are:

1 - The fee and royalty are not the same as the price as an end in itself for the service, but they are paid on the occasion of the performance of this service. While the price or the price covers a specific industrial or commercial commodity from which the purchaser has benefited alone. Annexed services, in other words, there can be no payment of a fee or royalty, yet the service remains valid, while the non-payment of the price automatically precludes the enjoyment of the service.

2 - In contrast to the price, fees and sometimes royalty are collected forcibly if not paid voluntarily, and thus its legal system is different as well. It can only be imposed in general by virtue of a law (Al-Khoury Abdullah, 1999, p. 265).

Third: The distinction between fee, royalty and tax.

A tax can be defined as a monetary obligation that an individual forcibly pays to the state or one of its public bodies as a final contribution to bearing public burdens and costs without obtaining a consideration or a special benefit. We have previously mentioned that it is possible to resort to coercive means to secure the payment of fees and royalty by the beneficiary or beneficiary of the ancillary service, and this is what makes it similar to tax in this respect, but they differ in other important and essential aspects, including:

1- The tax shall be imposed on the taxpayers and collected from them without any consideration.

2 - On the contrary, both the fee and royalty are collected in return for a specific service provided by the public utility to the beneficiary (Abdul MutaalZaki, 1941, p. 185).

The service on the basis of which fees and royalties are collected is very diverse, sometimes it is related to public utilities that have beneficiaries of a certain category who benefit from their services in particular, but nevertheless they are in the context of securing the public interest in its entirety or its general concept. The health facility is a public facility for all citizens, but the beneficiaries of it are the patients who go to benefit from its services. Likewise, the education facility is a public facility that achieves a public interest, but the real beneficiary is the student.

Section one: The authority competent to determine the fees for public utilities.

The issue of determining public utility allowances is one of the procedural elements of the government's work, and the French Council of State confirmed this in one of its rulings when it considered it an essential element of its competence in everything related to the matter of regulating public utilities (C.E, 4 May, 1906). This was also confirmed by the French Constitutional Council, which considered, for example, that the fee imposed on the services provided by the radio and television public utility is one of the matters of an organizational nature, which is the matter of imposing and determining its amount for the government (C.C, 30 Jan, 1968). This right is recognized by the government, whatever the nature of the facilities, whether administrative or economic (C.E, 8 Nov, 1929). As long as it is a manifestation of the regulatory authority, the administrative work to determine the tariff is undoubtedly subject to the principle of legality, and based on this, the French State Council is keen that the administration must abide by the principle of equality between the beneficiaries of this entity.

However, it is an exception to that. It seems that the judiciary prevents the public authority from imposing tariffs on the beneficiaries of purely administrative public utilities.

The judiciary may consider that the facilities entrusted with maintaining security and order, preventing the occurrence of disasters and calamities and dealing with their effects, are facilities established to achieve the collective interests of all people residing within their scope, and therefore the expenses incurred for this purpose are mandatory expenses that must be incurred. Any tariff, allowance, or consideration, unless the services required of them require additional expenses that are not usually obligatory, but are imposed by the interest of the beneficiaries themselves alone (CE, 10 Aug, 1918).

Through the provisions of the French administrative judiciary, it is clear that he distinguished between services and collective consumption factors for which the public utility may not receive any compensation, and those that include and on their occasion serve the individual interests of a beneficiary or a certain number of beneficiaries within the community

Which can therefore be imposed a tariff. And such a possibility is also present even when the service is of a purely collective nature, but at the same time it is used by one of them or some of them in a special way and in an unusual or unfamiliar way. However, it is difficult to determine the standard on which to describe This or that public service is of special and unusual use.

Therefore, the judiciary tried to be clear to the extent that the facts of the cases before it allow. It distinguishes between services originally and legally entrusted to purely administrative facilities, and for which there is no room for imposing any tariff on them as one of the public duties imposed on the public utility, so he alone must bear all of its expenses and burdens. (CE, Jan. 18, 1985). And between services that go beyond the normal needs and measures to protect individuals, which in this case become special services that are not usually required by public necessity. Therefore, the public utility has the right to impose on its beneficiaries a specific allowance (C.E, 5 Dec, 1984).

The second section: the policy used to determine the allowances.

This policy takes three aspects:

A - The symbolic tariff policy. It is as close as possible to free or it may take the status of (half free)

Here, the tariff is of a symbolic level. Either to make the beneficiaries understand that the service has a price, or to urge them to economize on consumption or excessive use. The administration, in order not to overburden its treasury with exorbitant expenses that most of them do not meet, may throw some of these burdens on the taxpayers in favor of the beneficiaries or beneficiaries. Those cover part of the expenses of the services that these people always benefit from at nominal prices, and thus the competent administrative authority avoids the risk of financial deficit that it may face if it bears all the expenses (J.Cohen, 1963, p.123).

B- Exorbitant tariff policy. And it rarely happens, as the beneficiary is obliged to pay the amount of the cost of the service rendered to him. With the addition of a fee imposed on it by law. Such as the granting of passports, driving licenses for vehicles, and some professional and industrial licenses....etc(Al-KhourySaad Allah, 1999, p. 274).

C - the policy of economic and financial balance. This policy requires measuring the allowance or tariff on the cost of the service. If this policy is desirable and indicates maturity and sympathy in the general social affairs, it remains unclear due to the large number of elements that interfere in the process of drawing it, and given the complexity of the concerns facing the government in this field, and therefore From this very standpoint, political whims and interests often dominate here at the expense of concrete economic and mathematical facts (Mescheriakoff, 1991, p. 206).

Conclusion

After we have finished our research, it is necessary for us to indicate the most important results that have been reached, with the necessary recommendations for this. May they touch the ears of the officials and try to solve it.

First: the results.

1 - The principle of free services did not apply to all types of public utilities, but was applied according to the type of facility. For purely administrative public facilities, they provide their services completely free of charge without the administration receiving any compensation from the beneficiaries. As for the semi-administrative public facilities, it appears that the administration receives from the beneficiaries. Tariffs in the form of fees, royalties and taxes. On the contrary, the economic public utilities are free of charge and provide their services to the beneficiaries for a price close to that of the private sector.

2 - Free public utility services are provided in constitutional texts, especially administrative public utilities, and their receipt is sometimes explicit and sometimes implicit.

3 - It was found through the research that the public administration in Iraq has deviated from what the constitution stipulated for it to provide services for free, as it tended to create special channels in some semi-administrative facilities to obtain sums of money from the beneficiaries that burden the citizen without relying on a legal text, which is evident in the annex General health and higher education.

4 - Although purely administrative facilities provide their services completely free of charge, it was found through research that the public administration in Iraq has gone to obtain fees from the beneficiaries of its services, especially in the facility of the Ministry of Interior, which is evident when the beneficiary obtains a passport or license Driving or transferring ownership of a vehicle, knowing that the amounts of these fees do not take into account the economic situation of the country and the monthly income of the individual.

Second: Recommendations:

1 - The legislator is obligated to the constitution and in order to prevent confusion with the explicit text on free public utility services.

2 - The need for the administration to abide by the provisions of the constitution in providing public services, and to adhere to the principle of equality in providing these services.

3- The administration should review the value of tariffs imposed on beneficiaries of public utility services, in proportion to the volume of services provided by the public utility.

4 - The need for semi-administrative public utilities to withdraw from the new channels they have developed, which impose high prices on the beneficiaries, given that these facilities provide their services free of charge according to the text of the constitution, and that what these utilities have developed contradicts the provisions of the constitution.

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